

FAQ - DrugProt corpus

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1. What is the goal of the track?

Solution: The goal is to predict the chemical-protein relations present in a set of abstracts. For that, we give you two sets (training and development) of abstracts, entities and relations manually annotated. Then, we will give you a set of abstracts and the entities they contain and you will have to return the predicted relationships.

2. *For the test set, is that correct that we will not have to perform the NER task and we can focus only on extraction relations from already provided entities?*

Solution: Yes that's correct. Mentions will be provided by the DrugProt organizers for the test set.

3. How testing procedure will be performed? Options:

a. No relations provided at all (we are expected to return all automatically predicted relations)

b. We are given a set of relations, where some are noisy and incorrect, and some are correct, and we need to identify the correct ones.

Solution: A (no relations provided, teams have to return them)

4. Does the training set contain all possible entities and types of relations between them?

In other words, are we expected to get entities/types of relations in the test set, which were not mentioned in the training set?

Solution: To make the task realistic, the test set might contain relations between certain entity pairs not seen previously in the training set. This means they actually have to be able to predict or extract such relations. There might be some previously seen relations between entity pairs (but they will not be many). This is actually the practical value of this track.

5. Can we use some information outside the training set to build our systems?

Solution: this is possible but such cases need to be described in the proceedings paper and the DrugProt questionnaire to be transparent and to be able to understand if using other data sources can improve the obtained results.

6. Entity marks are not unique. We see in the drugprot_training_entities.tsv that there are multiple annotations with the mark T1, T2, etc.

Solution: Entity marks (T15, T21, etc) are not unique. They are unique within each record! Then, every entity is identified by the combination of entity mark + PMID of its record. If you want to search for the entity T15, you must specify first to which file it belongs. If not, there will be multiple entities with the mark T15, but in different records.

7. The relationship file is, e.g.,

12488248 INHIBITOR Arg1:T1 Arg2:T52

Will "Arg1" always be the "chemical", and "Arg2" always be the "gene/protein"?

Solution: Yes. Arg1 are always CHEMICAL and Arg2 always GENE entities

8. Can a single CHEMICAL - GENE pair have multiple annotated relations?

Solution: Yes. A given pair can indeed have multiple relations if the context indicates so. This is usually the case for proteins/genes with multiple biological functions, but it is not very frequent that such descriptions are provided in a single publication. Indeed, in the training and development datasets, there are 26 CHEMICAL-GENE pairs with multiple labels.

For example, for PMID "16920841", the pair Arg1:T18 - Arg2:T37 has an ACTIVATOR relation as well as an INDIRECT-UPREGULATOR relation:

16920841 ACTIVATOR Arg1:T18 Arg2:T37
16920841 INDIRECT-UPREGULATOR Arg1:T18 Arg2:T37

9. How do I register?

Solution: Simply fill-in this form <https://forms.gle/cJtHdRfJhUiaLbb58>

As soon as you click on the SEND button you are officially registered.